

STUDIES ON THE PHYSICO-CHEMICAL AND ELECTROKINETIC PROPERTIES OF GELS OF SILICIC ACID AND ALUMINIUM HYDROXIDE AND SOME SYNTHETIC AND NATURAL ALUMINOSILICATES, SPECIALLY IN RELATION TO ION-EXCHANGE PHENOMENA.

By S. P. RAYCHAUDHURI AND A. K. M. QUDRAT GHANI.

In the present work the cation and anion exchange properties, buffer curve and electrokinetic properties of aluminosilicates of widely varying $\text{SiO}_2/\text{sesquioxide}$ ratios have been studied and these properties have been compared with similar properties of some naturally occurring aluminosilicates like kaolin, montmorillonite, halloysite, beidellite and limonite. Incidentally the co-precipitation of oppositely charged colloidal solutions was studied, by determining the $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratios of different precipitates obtained by mixing the sols in varying proportions; the amount of free alumina on free silica given off by the different precipitates have also been studied.

Ghosh and Bhattacharyya (*Soil Sci.*, 1930, 29, 311) have shown that mixed gels of silica and alumina and of silica and ferric oxide as obtained by mutual precipitation may have properties resembling in some respects those of the soil colloids, so far as adsorption of calcium and phosphate ions are concerned. Of the various investigations concerning the silica-sesquioxide ratio, reference may be made to those of Wiegner (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1931, 50, 31, 65), Mattson (*J. Agric. Res.*, 1926, 33, 553; *First Internat. Cong. Soil Sci.*, 1926, II, 199), Anderson (*J. Agric. Res.*, 1929, 38, 521), Bhattacharyya and Ganguli (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 204, 213), Bhattacharyya (*ibid.*, 1937, 14, 225) Sreenivasa (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1935, 1, 607; 2, 201; 1936, 3, 283). Although considerable work has been done on synthetic aluminosilicates, no parallelism appears to have been drawn between synthetic and naturally occurring aluminosilicates of widely varying $\text{SiO}_2/\text{sesquioxide}$ ratios. Such a study was felt to be desirable.

In the present paper the base exchange properties including the buffer curves and electrokinetic properties of synthetic aluminosilicates of widely varying $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratios, obtained by mixing oppositely charged sols of SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 , have been compared with similar properties of naturally occurring clay minerals e.g. kaolin, bauxite, halloysite, limonite and montmorillonite.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Preparation of Sols.

Silicic Acid Sol.—Silicic acid sol was prepared by adding concentrated hydrochloric acid to a 20% solution of sodium silicate (Merck) and by subsequent dialysis

Aluminium Hydroxide Sol.—A solution of aluminium chloride containing 2.45% of Al_2O_3 was taken and ammonia added to it. The precipitate was well washed with hot water and then transferred to a flask containing water, the actual proportions being 1 litre of water for every 5 g. of Al_2O_3 . The whole was then heated and kept boiling, and 0.05N hydrochloric acid added from a burette. After each addition, water was added to replace that boiled off. An opalescent liquid that could be filtered unchanged was obtained. The colloidal solution of aluminium hydroxide, thus prepared, was then subjected to dialysis in a parchment bag for several days, the p_x at the stage when dialysis was discontinued being found to be 5.8.

Synthetic Aluminosilicate.—The synthetic aluminosilicates were prepared by mixing silicic acid sol and aluminium hydroxide sol in varying proportions. The precipitates formed were at first washed by ordinary dialysis in a parchment bag and subsequently by electro-dialysis, until the anode was free of chlorine.

Electro-osmotic Experiment.

Electro-osmotic experiments with the precipitates were carried out by the modified method of Briggs, Bennet and Pierson (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1918, 22, 256). As recommended by Mukherjee (*Phil. Mag.*, 1922, 44, 103; *Nature*, 1922, 110, 732) and Mukherjee and Ray (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 173) the straight tube was replaced by a U-tube, thus doing away with the use of porous plugs or glass-wool.

Determination of the SiO_2/Al_2O_3 ratios of the various precipitates.—The procedure followed was that given in A.O.A.C., 1938 Ed.

Determination of Base Exchange Capacities and of Buffer Curves.—The base exchange capacities and buffer curves of synthetic and natural aluminosilicates were determined by the method devised by Schofield (*J. Agric. Sci.*, 1933, 20, 252), and followed by Raychaudhuri and Nandy-mazumdar (*Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1939, 2, 34; *Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 1940, 10, 62), Raychaudhuri, Sulaiman and Basuraychaudhuri, *ibid.*, 1941, 11, 603), and Raychaudhuri and Basuraychaudhuri (*ibid.*, 1942, 12, 137).

Determination of the Cataphoretic Speeds of Kaolin.—The cataphoretic speeds of kaolin were determined by means of the cataphoretic cell of

Fréundlich and Abramson (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, 128, 25; 1928; 133, 57; cf. also Northrup, *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1922, 4, 629 and Brown and Brown, *Brit. J. Expt. Path.*, 1929, 10, 61). The cataphoretic velocities of the particles at depths $\frac{1}{2}D$ and $\frac{2}{3}D$ were measured, the mean value being taken (cf. Smoluchowski, Graetz, "Handbuch der Elektrizität und Magnetismus," 1914, II, 306).

Determination of Free Silica and Free Alumina in the Synthetic Aluminosilicates.—The quantities of free silica and free alumina in the synthetic aluminosilicates were determined by following essentially the method of Drosdoff and Truog (*J. Amer. Soc. Agron.*, 1935, 27, 312).

Preparation of Aluminosilicates free of Alumina.—Following the procedure of Mattson (*Soil. Sci.*, 1931, 31, 311) the precipitates of silica, alumina and aluminosilicates were treated with a hot 10% solution of aluminium chloride to get rid of free alumina.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

Compositions of Silicic Acid and Aluminium Hydroxide Sols and of Precipitated Gels.

- (i) Conc. of silicic acid sol—1 mol of SiO_2 in 1164 c.c. of sol.
 (ii) Conc. of aluminium hydroxide sol—1 mol. of Al_2O_3 in 4548 c.c. of sol.
 (iii) Compositions of precipitated gels are shown in Table I.

TABLE I.

Mixing ratios of sols... ($\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$)	0.5	1.0	2.0	4.0	8.0	25.0	Silicic acid gel
Comp. ratios of the gels... ($\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$)	0.44	0.98	2.0	3.0	7.0	16.0	

In order to examine whether a precipitated mass can combine with silica on long standing, two types of silicic acid sols (dialysed for 3 and 4 days respectively) were mixed with a sample of alumina sol and the resulting precipitate was analysed after 5, 10 and 60 hours after mixing the sols. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II.

Silicic acid sol dialysed for	$\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ (mixing ratio = 2) after mixing Al_2O_3 sol with SiO_2 sol. after			
	1 hr.	5 hrs.	10 hrs.	60 hrs.
3 days	...	1.78	1.78	1.78
4	0.3	1.20	1.35	1.78

The sol dialysed for 4 days was acid-free and almost a gel. This experiment tends to show that aluminium can combine with silica even after lump formation.

The compositions of the residues after treatment with hot AlCl_3 solutions are shown in Table III and plotted graphically in Fig. 1.

TABLE III.

Mixing ratios of sols ($\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$) ..	0.5	1.0	2.0	4.0	8.0	25.0
Comp. ratios of the gels (") ...	0.67	1.21	1.78	1.78	4.96	5.41

FIG. 1.

In Fig. 1 from point I to A, the Al added gets combined with the compound having $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio=3 and as this compound exists in increasing amount from I to A, the amount of aluminosilicate that gets combined with Al increases in the same manner, so that eventually we get a straight line for this portion of the curve; the combination may be represented as:

From the point A to B the combination of Al with the aluminosilicate gets lesser due the fact that above the $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio=3, the complex gets

covered with free SiO_2 , resulting in a gradual retardation of the above reaction, because the alumina cannot get to the compound due to intervention of silica. That Al can combine with gellified Al-silicates is brought out in Table III.

From B onwards we again find a straight line. This we have tried to explain by assuming that at B the micelles get completely covered with free SiO_2 , and no chemical combination can henceforth take place; on treatment with AlCl_3 the aluminium added merely gets adsorbed on the previously adsorbed silica. Though this process of adsorption begins from A, and the slope AB is in part due to this effect, at B a maximum is reached, and the $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio remains steady near about 5. A further confirmation of the above theory presents itself when the electrokinetic and base-exchange properties of the compounds at A and A' are compared. Such a comparison tends to show that the samples A and A' are more or less alike. The millimols of silica and alumina per 100 g. of precipitated gels (oven dry basis) before and after treatment with a hot 10% solution of aluminium chloride were determined by treating these gels with a 2% solution of sodium carbonate at 70° for 10 hours (Drosdoff and Trug, *loc. cit.*) The results are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

A. Before treatment with 10% AlCl_3 .			B. After treatment with 10% AlCl_3 .		
Comp. ratio.	M. mols after treatment with 2% Na_2CO_3 soln.		Comp. ratio.	M mols after treatment with 2% Na_2CO_3 soln.	
$\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$.	SiO_2	Al_2O_3 .	$\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$.	SiO_2 .	Al_2O_3 .
0.44	Nil	257.4	0.67	Nil	85.2
0.98	"	104.3	1.21	"	26.3
2.00	61.6	Nil	1.78	22.1	63.4
3.00	85.4	"	1.78	24.3	65.1
7.00	163.3	"	4.96	88.3	197.6
16.00	455.9	"	5.41	210.7	276.2

We find from Table IV A that at lower ratios of $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ in the original precipitates, only free Al_2O_3 is given off, whereas at higher ratios SiO_2 alone is given off and in increasing quantities. Results in Table IV (A & B) show that in precipitates, where $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio is below 1.21 (*i.e.* where treatment with 10% hot AlCl_3 has resulted in peptisation of some free alumina), the quantity of alumina extracted with 2% Na_2CO_3 solution is less in the precipitated gels after treatment with hot AlCl_3 solution than before. Thus where the mixing ratio of $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ is 0.5 (*vide* Table I) the extracted alumina in millimols per 100 g. of gel reduces from 257.4 to 85.2. Also where

the mixing ratio of $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ is 1.00, this figure reduces to 26.3. Beyond this mixing ratio, however, treatment with 10% AlCl_3 has resulted in positive adsorption of alumina and we find that increasing quantities of alumina are being given off. Table IV also shows that the quantities of SiO_2 given off by treatment with 2% Na_2CO_3 solution becomes less after treatment with hot 10% AlCl_3 solution and in both cases SiO_2 given off increases as we pass down the column. This relative decrease of free SiO_2 (extracted with 2% Na_2CO_3 solution) and the increase in free Al_2O_3 extracted by the same process, after treatment of the precipitated gels with hot 10% AlCl_3 solution, explains the 'increase in positive charge after treatment of the precipitates with hot 10% AlCl_3 solution (*vide* Table V). It would be interesting to consider this decrease in the quantities of free SiO_2 (Tables IV and V) in the light of the postulations regarding the structure of these aluminium silicates given before. It has been already assumed that at high $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratios, much SiO_2 remains free imparting to the precipitate a negative charge (Table V). On treatment with hot AlCl_3 solution, three definite processes occur in successive stages (Fig. 1). At first there is a decrease in the alumina content of the precipitate and the quantity of free alumina decreases. Then in the second stage, treatment with hot AlCl_3 results in the combination of aluminium and the aluminium content of the precipitate increases and consequently the free alumina given off increases from 0 to 63.4 and 65.1. The quantity of free SiO_2 given off naturally decreases as most of it has combined with the aluminium. The charge is positive (*vide* Table V) as there is more of free alumina than free SiO_2 . Then in the third stage, aluminium is mostly adsorbed on the precipitate and some of it of course combines chemically with the SiO_2 . The result is that the quantity of free SiO_2 decreases after treatment with hot AlCl_3 and the quantity of free alumina given off greatly increases from 0 to 197.1 and 276.2, the charge becoming positive (*vide* Table V). Another interesting point in Table IV is that as we go down the column we find the quantity of free SiO_2 given off increases but the quantity of free alumina given off at first decreases from 85.2 to 26.3 and then increases from 63.4 to 276.2.

Electro-osmotic Experiments with Synthetic Gels of Aluminosilicates and with Silicic Acid Gel.

Table V shows the electro-osmotic movement in cm. per 5 mins. with the electro-dialysed precipitated gels of aluminosilicates (Table VA) and with the same gels after treatment with a hot 10% solution of aluminium chloride (Table VB).

TABLE V.

A. Electrodialysed precipitated gels of aluminosilicates.			B. Electrodialysed pptd. gels after treatment with hot 10% AlCl_3 and subsequently electro dialysed.		
Mixing ratio of sols ($\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$).	Comp. ratio of ppt. ($\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$).	Electro-osmotic movement (cm./5 min.).	Comp. ratio of ppt. ($\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$).	Electro-osmotic movement (cm./5 min.).	
0.50	0.44	+2.9	0.67	+2.5	
1.00	0.98	+1.0	1.12	+0.3	
2.00	2.00	-1.6	1.78	+2.0	
4.00	3.00	-2.3	1.78	+2.0	
8.00	7.00	-2.5	4.96	+3.3	
25.00	16.00	-4.8	5.41	+4.1	
Silicic acid gel	...	-5.9			

That in presence of AlCl_3 a reversal of charge might be effected is shown from the following data taken from Mattson (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE VI.

Electrodialysed Sharkey soil

(0.2 g. colloid per litre).

AlCl_3 (m. equivalent/litre)	...	0.0	0.2	1.0	1.5	2.0	4.0
μ /sec./volt/cm.	...	-3.2	-0.80	-0.17	± 0.00	+0.14	+0.49

Mattson has explained this reversal in charge by assuming the formation of compounds like oxychlorides, which dissociate into diffusible anions and an electropositive colloidal complex.

Electro-osmotic Experiments with Synthetic Gels of Aluminosilicates and with Silicic Acid Gel.

In the following tables (VII-XIX) I_{mol} represents the electro-osmotic movement of bubble for 5 min. in cm. for a salt MCl and I_{LiCl} represents similar movement for the salt LiCl . We may assume the intensity of adsorption to be proportional to the cataphoretic speed. The third column gives the value of $I_{\text{MCl}} - I_{\text{LiCl}}$. If we take I_{Li} to be zero, this reduces to I_{M} , thus giving the intensity of adsorption for a cation M relative to Li . Li is chosen due to the fact that among the cations taken, it has the weakest exchange intensity. Similarly the sixth

column of the tables $I_A = I_{NO_3}$ represents the intensity for an anion A (I_A). It may be pointed out that I_M is throughout positive and I_A is throughout negative. The strengths of various electrolytic solutions used are $N/500$ in all the cases. Electro-osmotic movement is expressed in $cm./5 \text{ min.}$

Tables VII to XIII give data for gels untreated with hot 10% $AlCl_3$ solution, whilst Tables XIV to XIX give data for gels treated with hot 10% $AlCl_3$ solution.

TABLE VII.

SiO_2/Al_2O_3 mixing ratio = 0.50.

„ composition „ = 0.44.

Salt used.	Movement.	$I_{MCl} - I_{LiCl} = I_M$.	Salt used.	Movement.	$I_{KA} - I_{KNO_3} = I_A$.
LiCl	+4.20	—	$K_4Fe(CN)_6$	-0.6	-7.10
NaCl	+4.3	0.1	K_2HPO_4	± 0.0	-6.5
KCl	+4.4	0.2	K_2SO_4	+2.4	-4.1
$MgCl_2$	+4.4	0.2	KCl	+4.4	-2.1
$CaCl_2$	+4.5	0.3	KI	+4.9	-1.6
$BaCl_2$	+4.5	0.3	KBr	+6.0	-0.5
$AlCl_3$	+4.7	0.5	KNO_3	+6.5	—
Water	+2.9	—	—	—	—

TABLE VIII.

SiO_2/Al_2O_3 mixing ratio = 1.00.

„ composition „ = 0.98.

Salt used.	Movement.	$I_{MCl} - I_{LiCl} = I_M$.	Salt used.	Movement.	$I_{KA} - I_{KNO_3} = I_A$.
LiCl	+1.7	—	$K_4Fe(CN)_6$	-0.5	-3.0
NaCl	+1.9	+0.2	K_2HPO_4	± 0.0	-2.5
KCl	+2.0	+0.3	K_2SO_4	+0.7	-1.8
$MgCl_2$	+2.2	+0.5	KCl	+2.0	-0.5
$CaCl_2$	+2.3	+0.6	KI	+2.0	-0.5
$BaCl_2$	+2.5	+0.8	KBr	+2.3	-0.2
$AlCl_3$	+2.7	+1.0	KNO_3	+2.5	—
Water	+1.0	—	—	—	—

TABLE IX.

SiO₂/Al₂O₃ mixing ratio = 2'00

,, composition ,, = 2'00

Salt used.	Movement.	$I_{MCl} - I_{LiCl} = I_M$	Salt used.	Movement.	$I_{KA} - I_{KNO_3} = I_A$
LiCl	-3'4	—	K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	-3'8	-1'0
NaCl	-3'1	+0'3	K ₂ HPO ₄	-3'5	-0'7
KCl	-2'9	+0'5	KI	-3'2	-0'4
MgCl ₂	-2'6	+0'8	K ₂ SO ₄	-3'2	-0'4
CaCl ₂	-2'4	+1'0	KBr	-3'0	-0'2
BaCl ₂	-2'2	+1'2	KCl	-2'9	-0'1
AlCl ₃	-1'8	+1'6	KNO ₃	-2'8	—
Water	-1'6	—	—	—	—

TABLE X.

SiO₂/Al₂O₃ mixing ratio = 4'00

,, composition ,, = 3'00

Salt used.	Movement.	$I_{MCl} - I_{LiCl} = I_M$	Salt used.	Movement.	$I_{KA} - I_{KNO_3} = I_A$
LiCl	-5'7	—	K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	-4'8	-0'4
NaCl	-4'8	+0'9	K ₂ HPO ₄	-4'7	-0'3
KCl	-4'4	+1'3	KI	-4'6	-0'2
MgCl ₂	-3'9	+1'8	K ₂ SO ₄	-4'6	-0'2
CaCl ₂	-3'5	+2'2	KBr	-4'5	-0'1
BaCl ₂	-3'1	+2'6	KCl	-4'4	0'0
AlCl ₃	-2'6	+3'1	KNO ₃	-4'4	—
Water	-2'3	—	—	—	—

TABLE XI.

SiO₂/Al₂O₃ mixing ratio = 8'00

,, composition ,, = 7'00

Salt used.	Movement.	$I_{MCl} - I_{LiCl} = I_M$	Salt used.	Movement.	$I_{KA} - I_{KNO_3} = I_A$
LiCl	-8'0	—	K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	-7'2	-0'3
NaCl	-7'3	+0'7	K ₂ HPO ₄	-7'2	-0'3
KCl	-7'0	+1'0	KI	-7'1	-0'2
MgCl ₂	-5'8	+2'2	K ₂ SO ₄	-7'1	-0'2
CaCl ₂	-4'9	+3'1	KBr	-7'0	-0'1
BaCl ₂	-4'1	+3'9	KCl	-6'9	0'0
AlCl ₃	-3'1	+4'9	KNO ₃	-6'9	—
Water	-2'5	—	—	—	—

TABLE XII.

SiO₂/Al₂O₃ mixing ratio = 25.0.

,, composition ,, = 16.0.

Salt used.	Movement in 1 min.	$I_{MCl} - I_{LiCl} = I_M$	Salt used.	Movement in 1 min.	$I_{KA} - I_{KNO_3} = I_A$
LiCl	-6.2	—	K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	-6.3	-0.2
NaCl	-6.1	+0.1	K ₂ HPO ₄	-6.2	-0.1
KCl	-6.1	+0.1	KI	-6.1	0.0
MgCl ₂	-5.9	+0.5	K ₂ SO ₄	-6.1	0.0
CaCl ₂	-5.6	+0.6	KBr	-6.1	0.0
BaCl ₂	-5.4	+0.8	KCl	-6.1	0.0
AlCl ₃	-5.0	+1.2	KNO ₃	-6.1	—
Water	-4.8	—	—	—	—

TABLE XIII.

Silicic acid gel.

Salt used.	Movement in 1 min.	$I_{MCl} - I_{LiCl} = I_M$	Salt used.	Movement in 1 min.	$I_{KA} - I_{KNO_3} = I_A$
LiCl	-6.2	—	K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	-6.2	0.0
NaCl	-6.2	0.0	K ₂ HPO ₄	-6.2	0.0
KCl	-6.2	0.0	KI	-6.2	0.0
MgCl ₂	-6.1	-0.1	K ₂ SO ₄	-6.2	0.0
CaCl ₂	-6.1	-0.1	KBr	-6.2	0.0
BaCl ₂	-6.1	-0.1	KCl	-6.2	0.0
AlCl ₃	-6.0	-0.2	KNO ₃	-6.2	0.0
Water	-5.9	—	—	—	—

TABLE XIV.

SiO₂/Al₂O₃ mixing ratio = 0.50.

,, composition ,, = 0.67.

Salt used.	Movement.	$I_{MCl} - I_{LiCl} = I_M$	Salt used.	Movement.	$I_{KA} - I_{KNO_3} = I_A$
LiCl	+1.3	—	K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	-0.1	-2.7
NaCl	+1.4	+0.1	K ₂ HPO ₄	+0.4	-2.2
KCl	+1.5	+0.2	K ₂ SO ₄	+1.0	-1.6
MgCl ₂	+1.7	+0.4	KCl	+1.5	-1.1
CaCl ₂	+1.8	+0.5	KI	+2.0	-0.6
BaCl ₂	+1.9	+0.6	KBr	+2.3	-0.3
AlCl ₃	+2.1	+0.8	KNO ₃	+2.6	—
Water	+2.5	—	—	—	—

TABLE XV.

SiO₂/Al₂O₃ mixing ratio = 1'0.

,, composition ,, = 1'12.

Salt used.	Movement.	$I_{MCl} - I_{LiCl} = I_M$.	Salt used.	Movement.	$I_{KA} - I_{KNO_3} = I_A$.
LiCl	+1'8	—	K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	-0'3	-3'1
NaCl	+2'0	+0'2	K ₂ HPO ₄	+1'5	-1'3
KCl	+2'3	+0'5	K ₂ SO ₄	+2'0	-0'8
MgCl ₂	+2'4	+0'6	KCl	+2'3	-0'5
CaCl ₂	+2'5	+0'7	KI	+2'5	-0'3
BaCl ₂	+2'6	+0'8	KBr	+2'6	-0'2
AlCl ₃	+2'9	+1'1	KNO ₃	+2'8	—
Water	+2'5	—	—	—	—

TABLE XVI.

SiO₂/Al₂O₃ mixing ratio = 2'00.

,, composition ,, = 1'78.

Salt used.	Movement.	$I_{MCl} - I_{LiCl} = I_M$.	Salt used.	Movement.	$I_{KA} - I_{KNO_3} = I_A$.
LiCl	+1'9	—	K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	-0'5	-3'9
NaCl	+2'2	+0'3	K ₂ HPO ₄	+1'5	-1'9
KCl	+2'4	+0'5	K ₂ SO ₄	+2'0	-1'4
MgCl ₂	+2'7	+0'8	KCl	+2'4	-1'0
CaCl ₂	+2'9	+1'0	KI	+2'7	-0'7
BaCl ₂	+3'1	+1'2	KBr	+3'0	-0'4
AlCl ₃	+3'3	+1'4	KNO ₃	+3'4	—
Water	+2'0	—	—	—	—

TABLE XVII.

SiO₂/Al₂O₃ mixing ratio = 4'00.

,, composition ,, = 1'78.

Salt used.	Movement.	$I_{MCl} - I_{LiCl} = I_M$.	Salt used.	Movement.	$I_{KA} - I_{KNO_3} = I_A$.
LiCl	+1'9	—	K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	-0'5	-4'0
NaCl	+2'2	+0'3	K ₂ HPO ₄	+1'5	-2'0
KCl	+2'4	+0'5	K ₂ SO ₄	+2'0	-1'5
MgCl ₂	+2'7	+0'8	KCl	+2'4	-1'1
CaCl ₂	+3'0	+1'1	KI	+2'7	-0'8
BaCl ₂	+3'1	+1'2	KBr	+3'0	-0'5
AlCl ₃	+3'3	+1'4	KNO ₃	+3'5	—
Water	+2'0	—	—	—	—

TABLE XVIII.

SiO₂/Al₂O₃ mixing ratio = 8'00.

,, composition ,, = 4'96.

Salt used.	Movement.	$I_{MCl} - I_{LiCl} = I_M$.	Salt used.	Movement.	$I_{KA} - I_{KNO_3} = I_A$.
LiCl	+1'9	—	KFe(CN) ₆	+0'1	-3'7
NaCl	+2'4	+0'5	K ₂ HPO ₄	+1'3	-2'5
KCl	+2'5	+0'6	K ₂ SO ₄	+2'0	-1'8
MgCl ₂	+2'9	+1'0	KCl	+2'5	-1'3
CaCl ₂	+3'1	+1'2	KI	+3'0	-0'8
BaCl ₂	+3'3	+1'4	KBr	+3'4	-0'4
AlCl ₃	+3'6	+1'7	KNO ₃	+3'8	—
Water	+3'0	—	—	—	—

TABLE XIX.

SiO₂/Al₂O₃ mixing ratio = 25'00.

,, composition ,, = 5'41.

Salt used.	Movement.	$I_{MCl} - I_{LiCl} = I_M$.	Salt used.	Movement.	$I_{KA} - I_{KNO_3} = I_A$.
LiCl	+2'1	—	K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	+0'3	-4'0
NaCl	+2'6	+0'5	K ₂ HPO ₄	+1'4	-2'9
KCl	+3'0	+0'9	K ₂ SO ₄	+2'4	-1'9
MgCl ₂	+3'4	+1'3	KCl	+3'0	-1'3
CaCl ₂	+3'8	+1'7	KI	+3'5	-0'8
BaCl ₂	+4'1	+2'0	KBr	+3'9	-0'4
AlCl ₃	+4'5	+2'4	KNO ₃	+4'3	—
Water	+4'1	—	—	—	—

TABLE XX.

Catholytic experiments with kaolin by Freundlich and Abramson's cell.

Salt used (N/500).	μ /sec/ volt/cm.	Salt used (N/500).	μ /sec/ volt/cm.	Salt used (N/500).	μ /sec/ volt/cm.	Salt used (N/500).	μ /sec/ volt/cm.
LiCl	-1'33	K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	-1'12	CaCl ₂	-0'59	KBr	-0'78
NaCl	-0'92	K ₂ HPO ₄	+1'12	BaCl ₂	-0'53	KCl	-0'76
KCl	-0'76	KI	-0'80	AlCl ₃	-0'42	KNO ₃	-0'74
MgCl ₂	-0'67	K ₂ SO ₄	-0'79	Water	-0'34	—	—

It will be found in Tables VII to XX that in general the difference of velocity from Ba⁺⁺ to Al⁺⁺⁺ is greater than any other difference and the

value for Al^{+++} more nearly approaches that for H^+ (the electrolysed sample). This is explained by the fact that Al^{+++} being a constituent ion fits in the general structure of the gel, and comes into closer contact with the nuclear structure. The works of Mukherjee and Fajans have shown that even gels may possess regular patterns like crystals (*cf.* Fajans and Backerath, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1921, 97, 478; Mukherjee and Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 173).

The results of these investigations show that the intensity of cation adsorption follows more or less the Hoffmeister series,

It might be that besides the thickness of the double layer (d) other factors might come into play, *e.g.*, the comparative dissociation of the ions entering and leaving, which amongst others modifies the cataphoretic speed and this dissociation decreases from Na^+ to Ca^{++} or Ba^{++} . There can be simultaneous anion and cation adsorption and that the migration micelles rather than being a definite measure of the intensity of adsorption is dependent on other factors as well, the chief among them being the dissociation of complex formed by molecular adsorption, the hydration and the kinetic energy of the ions (*cf.* Mukherjee, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1921, 16, 103). When these factors are allowed, especially the relative dissociation, we can get a comparative study of the intensity of adsorption. Thus we find that in general the order is $Fe(CN)_6^{IV} > HPO_4^{''} > SO_4^{''} > Br' > Cl' > NO_3'$. This more or less follows the lyotropic series which is $I' > Br' > Cl' > NO_3' > SO_4^{''}$. Though the position of $SO_4^{''}$ in the lyotropic series happens to be the last; $SO_4^{''}$ from H_2SO_4 has been known to be more strongly adsorbed in soil than Cl' , the order being $PO_4^{'''} > SO_4^{''} > Cl'$ (Mattson, 1929). This may be explained as being due to the presence of free sesquioxides in the samples.

With positively charged precipitates (Tables XIV to XIX) the positive charge decreases in the following order: $Al^{+++} > Ba^{++} > Ca^{++} > Mg^{++} > K^+ > Na^+ > Li^+$. The behaviour of anions shows that the positive charge diminishes in the following order: $NO_3' > Br' > I' > Cl' > SO_4^{''} > PO_4^{'''}$ $> Fe(CN)_6^{IV}$. With positively charged precipitate the charge is throughout negative in presence of $Fe(CN)_6^{III}$. This reversal of charge can be explained from Mukherjee's point of view (*loc. cit.*) as being due to the adsorption of the highly negatively charged $Fe(CN)_6^{III}$ ions in the primary sheet of the double layer. The latter imparts a negative charge to the whole particle. Our findings are that $Fe(CN)_6^{III}$ in all cases

decreases the positive charge to a large extent, though an actual reversal of sign may not occur when the initial charge is highly positive.

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

The results in Tables VII to XX have been plotted graphically in Figs. 2, 3, 4 and 5. Fig. 2 shows the value of I_A (intensity of adsorption of the cations relative to Li when the value for Li is taken to be zero) plotted against the percentage composition of the different precipitates (untreated with 10% hot AlCl₃). The curves show peaks, proving that at a region where the SiO₂ is 80-90%, the cation adsorption is maximum.

This is in accordance with the current views that at a particular $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio the cation adsorption is maximum (*cf.* Weigner, *loc. cit.*). Fig. 3 gives the value or I_a (intensity of adsorption of the anions relative to NO_3 , when the value for NO_3 is taken to be zero) plotted against the percentage composition of the precipitates. The curves show that the anion adsorption drops down with the SiO_2 content of the precipitates, pure SiO_2 gel showing zero intensity. This corroborates the suggestion of Mattson (*J. Agric. Res.*, 1926, 83, 553) that the adsorption of anions in soils is largely due to free sesquioxide. Bhattacharya and Ganguly (*loc. cit.*) have found a similar set of curves using a different method.

In Fig. 4 have been plotted the I_m values for gels treated with 10% AlCl_3 not against the percentage composition (some of the samples giving the same percentage composition, this method was not resorted to) but against the $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ mixing ratio of the sols when the precipitates were being formed. The $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ composition ratio curve was next superimposed and it was found that within moderate limits (here less than 5.4x $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio values) the intensity curve follows the composition ratio curve, *i.e.* within moderate limits of $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio values, the intensity of cation adsorption increases with SiO_2 content.

FIG. 4.

Dotted curve gives $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ comp. ratio.
Full-drawn curves give the volume of I_m .

In Fig. 5 similarly have been plotted I_a values for gels treated with 10% hot AlCl_3 solution. not against percentage composition, but have later been superimposed on the composition ratio curve and the curve for free alumina content (*i.e.* the Al_2O_3 which is liberated on treatment with 2% Na_2CO_3 , *cf.* Table II). Here we find that the intensity curves follow this latter curve, thus again showing that anion adsorption is connected with free sesquioxide content and not with the total sesquioxide content. $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{IV}$ does not give a minimum. Our findings are that this ion, in

all cases, decreases the positive charge though a reversal may occur only when the initial positive charge is rather weak. It may be mentioned

FIG. 5.

Dotted curve gives the comp. of the ppt. (% of total Al_2O_3).
Full-drawn curves give I_A and broken curves give free Al_2O_3 content.

that I_A includes the charge of the colloid, and this latter depends on the initial positive charge of the particle and on the amount of ion adsorbed. Both these factors increase with the increase of free alumina, but while the effect of the former is to increase the positive charge, that of the latter is to decrease it and I_A will merely give the relative difference of the two opposite process. In the case of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$, during the first part of curve (left side) the former effect is stronger i.e. the particle becomes initially relatively less positively charged due to less of free alumina as compared with the loss in negative charge due to less of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ being adsorbed.

Table XX shows the variation of electrical charge of electro dialysed kaolin with different anions and cations. The results show that the adsorption of cations follows the Hoffmeister's series, viz., $\text{Al}^{+++} > \text{Ba}^{++} > \text{Ca}^{++} > \text{Mg}^{++} > \text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{Li}^+$. Also the adsorption of anions follows the order, $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-} > \text{HPO}_4^{2-} > \text{I}^- > \text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{Br}^- > \text{Cl}^- > \text{NO}_3^-$. These orders of cationic and anionic adsorptions are similar to those found for the negatively charged gels and are in complete agreement with the theories of ion adsorption put forward by Mukherjee, (*loc. cit.*).

Determination of Buffer Curves.

The results are shown in Tables XXI, XXII and XXIII. The corresponding buffer curves have been drawn in Figs. 6, 7 and 8.

TABLE XXI.

Base-uptake per 100 g. original in m. equivalents electro dialysed precipitated gels (oven-dry basis).

p_H .	SiO ₂ .	Ratio of SiO ₂ to Al ₂ O ₃ equals to					Al ₂ O ₃ .
		1.	2.	4.	8.	25.	
1'3	-11'3	- 72'5	- 87'5	- 60'0	- 42'5	- 35'0	+1'8
2'9	-16'5	- 87'0	- 77'5	- 55'1	- 35'1	- 27'1	+2'2
4'6	+ 1'0	- 30'0	- 39'1	- 23'7	- 9'8	± 0'0	+6'8
7'1	+ 1'5	+125'0	+140'0	+180'1	+192'7	+120'1	+12'8
9'8	+17'1	+187'5	+179'0	+226'3	+237'5	+193'7	+107'2
12'5	+37'0	+207'5	+190'0	+247'5	+262'6	+237'6	+149'0

TABLE XXII.

Base-uptake in milliequivalents per 100 g. of precipitated and electro dialysed gels after treatment with 10% hot AlCl₃ solution and subsequent electro dialysis (oven-dry basis).

p_H	Ratio of SiO ₂ to Al ₂ O ₃ equals to				
	1.	2.	4.	8.	25.
1'3	- 52'5	- 20'1	- 9'0	- 32'3	- 4'9
2'9	- 63'2	- 29'7	- 13'1	- 37'5	- 7'6
4'6	+ 17'5	- 2'1	+ 12'5	+ 72'5	+224'9
7'1	+48'0	+181'5	+267'6	+213'7	+126'9
9'8	+54'5	+267'5	+320	+297'4	+470'2
12'5	+57'5	+310	+337'6	+350	+491'8

TABLE XXIII. *

Base-uptake per 100 g. of electro dialysed kaolin (oven-dry basis).

Minerals.	$p_H \rightarrow$ 1'3	2'9	4'6	7'1	9'8	12'5
Bauxite	-0'94	-0'51	-0'26	+2'2	+8'8	+18'0
Halloysite	-8'5	-3'6	-2'6	+0'38	+9'5	+34'3
Kaolin	0'0	+4'2	+4'2	+4'5	+7'0	+18'0
Limonite	-1'5	-1'8	-3'1	-0'88	+0'75	+11'8
Montmorillonite	-5'1	-1'7	-1'5	+0'38	+4'5	+10'5

* Data taken from the paper of Raychaudhuri and Basuraychaudhuri *loc. cit.* p. 145.)

It will be observed from Fig. 6 that the uptake of base by pure gels of silica and alumina are comparatively small. The uptake of base is

M. equiv. of the base taken per 100 g. of sol (oven-dry basis).

FIG. 6.

The numbers against the curves refer to the mixing ratio $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$.

greatest with precipitated gel having $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3=8$. This is in accordance with current view (*cf.* Weigner, *loc. cit.*) that at a particular $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio the base exchange capacity is a maximum. The conclusions from ion adsorption experiments (*vide* Fig. 2) also point to such a maximum. But the uptake of acid ($\text{HCl } 0.04N$, *vide* Tables XXI and XXII) does not give a maximum with high $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ values. This is due to the acidic nature of SiO_2 . Also the base combining capacity of sample with $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio=1 is higher than with a sample with $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio=2. This may be explained by the fact that a large amount of aluminium facilitates both acid and base uptake due to the ampholytoid nature of alumina. But pure alumina does not give high values, as the pure gel loses its structure. Fig. 7 shows that precipitates with silica-alumina ratios of 2 and 4 give buffer curve which are similar, only a shift to the acid side happens, corroborating the view postulated before that these two samples would, to some extent, show similar properties. As expected, precipitates with silica-alumina ratios of 8 and 25 give dissimilar curves. Precipitate with silica-alumina ratio of 1 gives a curve which has got the highest buffer capacity. All the curves in Fig. 7

FIG. 8.

have one characteristic *i.e.* at low p_H the acid uptake decreases with decrease of p_H . This may be due to the presence of aluminium ions on the surfaces of the precipitates, set free by treatment with hot $AlCl_3$ solution (*cf.* the buffer curve for Al_2O_3 gel in Fig. 8 at low p_H values). Fig. 8 shows that of all the clay-forming minerals studied, halloysite possesses maximum buffer capacity, next in order being montmorillonite and bauxite. Kaolin and limonite possess very low buffer capacity.

A comparison of Fig. 8 shows that the buffer curves of the naturally occurring minerals do not correspond much in nature to the buffer curves obtained with electrolysed precipitated gels of aluminosilicates and of the same gels after treatment with hot 10% $AlCl_3$ solution and subsequent electrolysis. Moreover, the buffer capacities of the naturally occurring minerals are much lower compared to those of the synthetic gels. This dissimilarity in the nature of the buffer curves of the synthetic and naturally occurring clay-forming aluminosilicates suggests that ageing of the precipitates may have considerably altered their properties. It would therefore be interesting to compare the properties of synthetic aluminosilicate gels after considerable ageing and of naturally occurring aluminosilicates which could not be undertaken in the present work.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
DACCA UNIVERSITY,
DACCA.

Received April 15, 1942.
